

Reflection/Refraction and Quantum Dynamic Probability Included in Special Relativity?

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In a previous note (1) we argued that quantum square root probabilities follow from the consideration of light reflecting and refracting at a surface along the y direction at $x=0$. No knowledge of Maxwell's periodic photon electric field is needed. The photon number and energy are conserved at a single photon level, but flux/intensity may be included through (2) $AA/c1 = BB/c1 + CC/c2$ where AA is the intensity of the incident beam ($AA>0$), BB the reflected and CC the refracted. There are two unknowns B,C if A is known and one equation which may be broken into two $A+B=C$ and $A/c1 - B/c1 = C/c2$. For $n1<n2$ (n =index of refraction $B<0$). Thus we argue that there is an underlying square root probability.

In this note we first heuristically suggest the form for the square root probability. A key point is that "particle" features such as E and p (for a photon) govern the dynamical wavelike probability. This also applies to a particle with rest mass. We also ask why this square root probability has not appeared in dynamical theories and argue that it appears in special relativity (i.e. a Lorentz boost) for a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$. As seen from a frame moving at constant speed $-v$, this particle moves with speed v . Thus $x'=vt'$, yet a 2x2 Lorentz transformation is applied to $(x=0, t=t_0)$. Only one relation is needed because $x'=vt'$ and $p'=E'/cc v$ suffice to yield the variables x' and p' . Thus we argue that a Lorentz transformation describes more than is necessary for a simple particle. The 2x2 nature of the problem we suggest describes more than a simple particle. It leads to the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, but $x=vt$ so why should x and t appear as if independent? We argue that $-Et+px=A$ is compatible with $dA/dx |_{\text{constant } t} = p$ and $dA/dt |_{\text{constant } x} = -E$. P and E are "particle/photon" properties, but $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$ represent eigensolutions of $-id/dx$ and id/dt . Thus if x and t are independent $\exp(ipx)$ may be interpreted as existing at all x points (as there is no time). This is the picture of an unusual probability which is two dimensional, with components which may be positive or negative as in the reflection/refraction problem. Thus we argue that the notion of a wave probability or square root probability not only exists in the reflection/refraction problem, but in the case of special relativity with what looks like an unnecessary 2x2 matrix from the point of view a particle ($m_0, x=0, t=t_0$) describing an associated square root wave like probability completely dependent on the particle properties E and p.

Reflection/Refraction

We briefly revisit the case of light A moving in the positive x direction reflecting B and refracting C at a surface y at $x=0$ as analyzed in (1). Often (2) this problem is solved using the continuity of the photon electric field, written as $A\exp(ipx)$, and its first derivative. "X" is then set to 0. In (1) we argued that no notion of Maxwell's electromagnetic equations and the resulting periodic photon electric field is needed.

A single photon conserves its energy and number whether it reflects or refracts, but there is a probability "a" for reflection and 1-a for refraction. One may not say that given the two options, the probabilities are $\frac{1}{2}$ and $\frac{1}{2}$. Then on what are they based? We argue that flux or flow is

important and conservation of energy (based on time grouping) does not include flux. One may write conservation of energy in terms of flux/intensity defining the latter as $E \cdot N \cdot c$ where E is the photon energy, N the number of photons and c the speed. Thus one has a kind of flux, AA for the incident beam, BB for the reflected and CC for the refracted in a steady state system which does not include time. AA is used to show explicitly that the flux is positive. Conservation of energy/particle number is equivalent to (2):

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((1))$$

and is associated with time grouping. For a steady state scenario there is no time, but rather a physical grouping in space with the incident and reflected beams being together for $x < 0$ and the refracted for $x > 0$. Thus:

$$AA/c_1 - BB/c_1 = CC/c_2 \quad \text{or} \rightarrow \quad A+B=C \quad \text{and} \quad A/c_1 - B/c_1 = C/c_2 \quad ((2))$$

Thinking in terms of a kind of square root flux balance in space yields two equations which allow for the solution of B, C in terms of A . Thus one introduces a strange square root flux because the regular flux equation ((1)) does not solve the problem. We note that given that the energy of each photon is E , one may multiply ((2)) by E and use $E/c = p$. Then one has a space grouped square root flux continuity equation together with a kind of momentum times square root flux continuity equation. This is enough to solve the reflection/refraction problem, but how does the square root flux probability behave in space?

Heuristic Arguments for the Square Root Flux Probability (Dynamic Probability) In Space

In the reflection/refraction problem we argued that some kind of balance of flux related information is key, but simply using flux to establish an energy/photon number equation ((1)) is not sufficient. The square root of the intensity/flux, however, "works". This square root flux, however, is associated with p , the momentum of the photon. Thus the notion of photon (particle like object) 's E and p are still present and directly affect square root flux equations. In fact the equation $Ap_1 - p_1B = p_2C$ could be written as:

$$[\text{Momentum Operator}] * (A-B-C) = 0 \quad ((3))$$

The question which arises is: What is the form of the square root flux and why is it a square root in the first place? If one thinks in terms of probability, the intensity/flux is a constant in space, but this removes the notion of speed crucial to flux. In $p_1A - Bp_1 = p_2C$ it is $1/c$ or p which appears so this should be the distinguishing feature of the square root probability flux. We argue that if there is no time, as in a steady state problem, probability should exist at all x , depend on p and have the possibility of being negative because $B < 0$ for $n_1 < n_2$ where n is the index of refraction. Furthermore the square root flux probability should distinguish the direction of motion. Heuristically one may suggest that:

$$\text{Constant } d/dx \text{ square root flux} = p \text{ square root flux} \quad ((4))$$

This suggests a square root flux which depends on px , exhibits some kind of translational invariance and is linked to a constant flux. I.e. squaring a px dependent square root flux should yield a flux constant in space. This leads to the candidate:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is complex or two dimensional to distinguish between p and $-p$ (i.e. direction), contains components which may be negative to cancel square root flux and depends on p , the photon particle-like property. Thus particle wave duality is contained in the square root flux probability. The above arguments are linked to the reflection/refraction of light, but may also be applied to a particle with rest mass.

One may ask: Why has this wavelike square root probability not appeared before in theories of dynamics? Why is a heuristic form presented?

(It appears in the electric field solution for a photon in Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, but that is not a dynamical theory of a particle.)

Special Relativity and the Square Root Flux Probability

Special relativity introduces the Lorentz matrix which transforms four-vectors such as (p, E) and (x, t) into (p', E') , (x', t') i.e. the variables as seen from a frame moving at a constant speed of $-v$. This matrix and its associated metric lead to the invariants: $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$) and $-Et + px$.

We consider the problem of a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$. A frame moving at $-v$ would see a particle moving with $x'/t'=v$. In other words x' and t' are directly linked and there is no need for a 2×2 matrix i.e.

$$|G(v) \quad vG(v)| \quad ((6)) \quad \text{where } G(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$$

$$|vG(v) \quad G(v)|$$

$t'=t_0 G(v)$ and $x'=vt'$. Only one dimension is needed for both E and t . For example, consider the case of m_0 and $p=0$ transforming to $G(v)m_0$ and $p=G(v)m_0 v$ with $c=1$. $G(v)$ is unknown in such a case and p is defined as a kind of energy flux. From the photon equation $E=pc$, momentum should be multiplied by c to have the same units as energy. In such a case pc is less than E and $E=m_0$ if $v \rightarrow 0$. Furthermore one should remove the sign of p . The simplest way to arrange for this is to use $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$). We argue one does not necessarily need a 2×2 matrix to establish $G(v)$ or calculate both x' and t' and E' and p' for the $m_0, x=0, t=t_0$ problem. In other words, even though the 2×2 matrix solves the problem (and includes various properties from linear algebra) it may contain more information than simply that applicable to a particle moving with $x'=vt'$.

To see this more closely consider the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ from the 2×2 matrix. $x'=vt'$ so x and t should not be written independently, at least for the example of $m_0, x=0, t=t_0$. $-Et + px$ is exactly of the form of the heuristic square root flux probability $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$.

The point we wish to make is that if $A = -Et + px$ separates t and x , then px exists in all of space, but grows. $dA/dx = p$, but the eigensolution $-id/dx \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ does not grow and covers all of space like a probability in a steady state scenario. It is based on the particle values p, E , but contains more information. $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ which describes the fact that all x points are the same at the intensity level, but at the square root probability level, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$, there exists periodic behaviour and complete dependence on p . We argue that what seems like an unnecessary 2×2 matrix to describe $m_0, x=0, t=t_0$ from a moving frame actually contains particle information associated with the transformation i.e. E', p' , but also the notion of a square root flux $\exp(ipx)$ probability. Thus we argue that the quantum wave is already contained in the form of special relativity as well as in the reflection/refraction example.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the quantum notion of a square root probability is present in the reflection/refraction of light problem. In particular, light A moves in the positive x direction, strikes a medium along y at $x=0$ and reflects B and refracts C . Each photon remains intact and retains its energy E , thus energy and photon number are conserved. This still leaves the value of the probability for reflection "a" unknown. (The probability for refraction is $1-a$.) Thus conservation of energy or photon number does not solve this problem. What is the underlying physical idea which governs the probability of reflection/refraction. We argue that intensity/flux $= E \cdot N \cdot c$ (where N is the number of photons and E the energy) seems to be important especially in a steady state situation. Conservation of energy yields: $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ where AA, BB and CC are the intensities of the incident, reflected and refracted rays. One is still no closer to solving for B and C in terms of A . Writing $AA/c_1 - BB/c_1 = CC/c_2$ i.e. removing time (as in a steady state situation) and grouping by space leads to the notion of a difference of squares and square root flux values i.e. $A+B=C$ and $A/c_1 - B/c_1 = C/c_2$. One may use $E=pc$ to show the latter is equivalent to $pA - pB = pC$. Thus it is as if one has square root fluxes which are conserved in space as well as their average momentum being conserved. Thus the notion of a square root flux, linked to the particle value p (thinking of the photon momentum as the property of a particle), seems to physically govern the reflection/refraction problem.

Heuristically one may guess the spatial form of such a square root flux probability. We suggest (based on a number of reasons given above) that it should be $\exp(ipx)$, but why does this not appear formally in a dynamical theory? We argue it does, namely in special relativity. At first it seems special relativity only describes particle features i.e. there is no notion of a square root flux probability $\exp(ipx)$. On further examination, however, we note that for the problem of a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$ one does not need the two-vector (x', t') as $x' = vt'$. Thus a 2×2 Lorentz matrix seems like "extra information", even though it does yield $x' = vt'$. In this problem, only one dimension is needed because p follows from E i.e. $p' = E'/cc v$ and x' from t' .

The 2×2 nature of the matrix, however, leads to the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ which presents x and t as independent variables while $x' = vt'$. We ask: How may one use px throughout space with time removed? $dA/dx = p$, but $-id/dx \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$. Thus an eigenvalue solution describes an unusual function which is two dimensional to distinguish between p and $-p$ (i.e. motion direction), maps to 1 i.e. $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$, contains dynamics (i.e. is dependent on the particle value p) and allows for interference of probability (i.e. two

$\exp(ipx)$'s or a phase shifted one may remove flux in certain regions etc). Thus we argue that particle features i.e. E, p are present in special relativity, but they govern the behaviour of an also present dynamical /square root flux type probability $\exp(ipx)$. This dynamical probability is present because of the dimensionality of the Lorentz matrix which treats x, t separately when for $[m_0$ at $x=0, t=t_0]$ only one and not two dimensions are needed. It is exactly the two dimensions that yield $-Et+px$ with independent x, t and ultimately lead to the wavelike square root probability $\exp(ipx)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Information, Quantum Probability and Reflection/Refraction (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change